

Effectiveness of Hoffman's exercise on flat nipples among Primigravida mothers residing at selected community areas

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Nipple abnormalities such as flat and inverted nipples are a condition with a prevalence of 10% to 20%. Moreover, it is most frequent during the first few days after giving birth, which inhibits successful breastfeeding. The majority of postpartum mothers are unable to breastfeed their newborns effectively due to breast difficulties including flat and inverted nipples, so despite great efforts, the practical concerns with breastfeeding continue to increase and flourish. Thus, providing education about breastfeeding has proven to be an effective intervention to increase exclusive breastfeeding.

Objectives:

To assess the effectiveness of Hoffman's exercise in improving nipple protraction in primigravida mothers with flat nipples.

Methods:

A quantitative, Quasi-experimental one group pre-test post-test research design was adopted. The study was conducted among 30 Primigravida mothers with flat nipple selected using non-probability convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured demographic proforma, Modified nipple grading scale, and LATCH Scale. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics including Chi-square test were used for comparison and association analysis.

Results:

The study findings revealed that the Pre-intervention assessment showed that none of the mothers had normal nipples, with the majority presenting Grade 2 (40%), followed by Grade 1 (30%) and Grade 3 (26.67%) flatness. Following the intervention, 40% of mothers achieved normal nipple status, with a notable reduction in higher grades, indicating significant improvement. Breastfeeding outcomes were favourable, with 70% of mothers attaining good LATCH scores, 16.67% moderate, and 13.33% poor outcomes. Statistical analysis using the Chi-square test revealed a significant association between the effectiveness of Hoffman's exercise and age ($\chi^2=6.24$, $p=0.044$), educational qualification ($\chi^2=8.32$, $p=0.040$), and type of family ($\chi^2=4.27$, $p=0.039$). However, no significant association was observed with gestational age ($\chi^2=5.18$, $p=0.159$) and occupation ($\chi^2=3.11$, $p=0.211$).

Conclusion:

Hoffman's exercise was effective in improving nipple protraction among primigravida mothers, resulting in better nipple grading and enhanced breastfeeding outcomes.

Keywords: Hoffman's exercise, Flat nipple, Primigravida mothers, Nipple protraction, demographic variables.

INTRODUCTION

Breastfeeding is universally recognized as the most effective, natural, and economical method of providing optimal nutrition to newborns. Successful breastfeeding depends on several maternal factors, among which the structure and protractility of the nipple play a vital role. Nipple protrusion is essential for proper latch-on, effective suckling, and sustained milk transfer. However, a considerable number of primigravida mothers experience flat or poorly protracted nipples, which may lead to breastfeeding difficulties, maternal frustration, nipple trauma, and early discontinuation of breastfeeding.

Flat nipples often fail to extend adequately during infant suckling, making it challenging for the infant to grasp the areola and maintain an effective latch. Nipple morphology varies widely among women and is influenced by genetic, physiological, and hormonal factors. Flat nipples are characterized by limited elevation above the areolar surface and poor elasticity, resulting in inadequate protrusion when stimulated. This anatomical variation, though not pathological, can impair the initiation of breastfeeding and delay early bonding between the mother and newborn. Early identification and timely intervention are crucial to prevent breastfeeding problems and promote exclusive breastfeeding as recommended by WHO.

Several non-invasive strategies have been developed to improve nipple protraction, among which Hoffman's exercise is one of the most commonly used techniques. Hoffman's exercise involves gentle, repeated stretching of the nipple base to break sub areolar adhesions and enhance protrusion. It is simple, cost-effective, safe, and can be performed by mothers independently. Evidence suggests that regular practice of Hoffman's exercise during antenatal and early postnatal periods may significantly improve nipple protractility and enhance breastfeeding outcomes.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

In women who are pregnant for the first time, it is very common that the nipple may not protrude fully. About one-third of mothers will experience some degree of inversion, but as the skin changes and become more elastic during pregnancy. flat nipple is commonly available in primipara mothers. During postnatal periods nipple abnormalities are often encountered in clinical practice in relation to lactation problem. One of the most advantageous and natural acts as a mother can do for her baby is breastfeeding. Breastfeeding is beneficial for both mother and child and its help for the present and future health of the child. It also helps in brain development and makes baby mentally and physically strong.

The abnormalities of the nipple include long nipple, short nipple, abnormally large nipple, inverted nipple, flat nipple, retracted nipple and cracked or damaged nipple. Nipple problem should not interfere in the breastfeeding process if proper guidance and counselling are provided to the mother during postnatal periods. Sometimes mothers stop breastfeeding due to these nipple problems and baby didn't get benefits of colostrum's. An evaluation was made that 10% of pregnant women have inverted or non-projectile nipples which delay breastfeeding.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Breastfeeding is recognized as a powerful means to support the Global Strategy for Women's, Children's, and Adolescents' Health (2016–2030), which aims to eliminate preventable deaths within a generation, as outlined in the Sustainable Development Goals. Throughout history, breastfeeding has been viewed as a fundamental human practice crucial for infant survival. The World Health Organization universally recommends exclusive breastfeeding for the first 6 months of an infant's life.

Breast problems are highly prevalent during the postnatal period. Globally, the incidence rate of breast engorgement is approximately 1 in 8000, while in India it is around 1 in 6500. About 20.0% of postnatal mothers, particularly first-time mothers, experience breast engorgement within 4 days after giving birth. According to the Grampian study, 33.0% of women encounter breast issues within the first 2 weeks postpartum, with 28.0% experiencing them thereafter. This figure may be conservative, as some women might attribute these issues to difficulties with breastfeeding. Apart from mastitis, which is relatively uncommon, these problems may include engorgement, soreness, cracked or bleeding nipples, and inverted nipples.

METHODOLOGY

The present study adopted a quantitative research approach with a Quasi-experimental one group pre-test post-test design to assess the effectiveness of Hoffman's exercise on flat nipples among primigravida mothers residing at selected community areas. The study was conducted in selected community areas over a period of 28 days. The target population included primigravida mothers with flat nipples in residing at selected areas. A total sample of 30 primigravida mothers was selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a selected demographic variable, Modified Nipple grading scale and LATCH Scale. The tool was validated by experts and reliability was established prior to the study. A pilot study was conducted to assess feasibility. Ethical approval was obtained and informed consent was taken from participants before data collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics

RESULT

SECTION I

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE

Age

Half of the primigravida mothers (50.00%) belonged to the 20–25 years age group, followed by 40.00% in the 25–30 years age group. Only 10.00% of the participants were in the 30–35 years age group.

Gestational Age:

The highest proportion of mothers (43.33%) were between 38–38.6 weeks of gestation, followed by 26.67% between 37–37.6 weeks. About 23.33% of the mothers were between 39–39.6 weeks, while 6.67% had a gestational age of 40 weeks or more, indicating that most participants were in the late antenatal period.

Educational Qualification:

An equal proportion of primigravida mothers (36.67% each) had primary and secondary education. About 16.67% of the participants were graduates, while 10.00% had no formal education, indicating varying educational backgrounds among the mothers.

Occupation:

Half of the primigravida mothers (50.00%) were housewives, whereas 30.00% were employees, and 20.00% were self-employed.

Type of Family:

A slightly higher proportion of participants (53.33%) belonged to nuclear families, while 46.67% were from joint families.

Section II**Analysis of Data Related to Effectiveness of Hoffman's Exercise on Nipple Protraction.****Pre-Interventional Assessment of Nipple Protraction**

Table 1: Distribution of Primigravida Mothers According to Pre-Interventional Nipple Grading

n=30

Nipple Grade	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Grade 0 – Normal	0	00.00
Grade 1 – Minimally flat	09	30.00
Grade 2 – Moderately flat	12	40.00
Grade 3 – Severely flat	08	26.67
Grade 4 – Inverted	01	03.33
Total	30	100.0

n=30

Figure no.1: Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of primigravida mothers according to pre-interventional nipple grading

Description: Above table and graph shows that in the study Most primigravida mothers had some degree of nipple flatness, with the highest proportion (40%) having Grade 2 (moderately flat) nipples, followed by Grade 1 (30%) and Grade 3 (26.67%). Only 3.33% had Grade 4 (inverted) nipples, and none had normal nipples (0%).

Post-Interventional Assessment of Nipple Protraction

Table 2: Distribution of Primigravida Mothers According to Post-Interventional Nipple Grading.

n=30

Nipple Grade	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Grade 0 – Normal	12	40.00
Grade 1 – Minimally flat	09	30.00
Grade 2 – Moderately flat	06	20.00
Grade 3 – Severely flat	03	10.00
Grade 4 – Inverted	00	00.00
Total	30	100.0

Figure no 2: Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of primigravida mothers according to post-interventional nipple grading

Description: Above table and graph shows that in the study After the intervention, most mothers showed improvement, with 40% achieving Grade 0 (normal) nipples. This was followed by 30% with Grade 1, 20% with Grade 2, and 10% with Grade 3, while none had Grade 4 (inverted) nipples, indicating the effectiveness of the intervention.

Comparison of Pre- and Post-Interventional Nipple Grading

Table 3: Comparison of Pre- and Post-Interventional Nipple Grading

n = 30

Nipple Grade	Pre-Intervention		Post-Intervention	
	F	%	F	%
Grade 0 – Normal	0	00.00	12	40.00
Grade 1 – Minimally flat	09	30.00	09	30.00
Grade 2 – Moderately flat	12	40.00	06	20.00
Grade 3 – Severely flat	08	26.67	03	10.00
Grade 4 – Inverted	01	03.33	00	00.00
Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Figure no 3: Bar diagram showing percentage wise Distribution of Primigravida Mothers According to Pre-Interventional and Post-Interventional Nipple Grading

Description: Above table and graph show that in the study Pre-intervention, 0% had Grade 0 nipples, while most had Grade 2 (40%), followed by Grade 1 (30%), Grade 3 (26.67%), and Grade 4 (3.33%). Post-intervention, improvement was seen with 40% achieving Grade 0, 30% in Grade 1, 20% in Grade 2, and only 10% in Grade 3, with 0% in Grade 4. Overall, the shift from higher to lower grades indicates the effectiveness of the intervention.

SECTION – III

Analysis of Data Related to Breastfeeding Outcomes Using Post-Interventional LATCH Scale

Table 4: Distribution of Primigravida Mothers According to Post-Interventional LATCH Scores.

n=30

LATCH Score Level	Score Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Poor	0–3	4	13.33
Moderate	4–7	5	16.67
Good	8–10	21	70.00
Total		30	100.0

Figure no 4: Bar diagram showing percentage wise Distribution of Primigravida Mothers According to Post-Interventional LATCH Scores.

Description: Above table and graph shows that in the study Post-intervention, 70% of mothers had good LATCH scores (8–10), 16.67% had moderate scores (4–7), and 13.33% had poor scores (0–3). Overall, the majority achieved good breastfeeding outcomes, indicating the effectiveness of the intervention.

SECTION – IV

To find the association between effect of Hoffman’s exercise with selected demographical variables.

Table:5 Association between Effect of Hoffman’s Exercise and Selected Demographic Variables among Primigravida Mothers

n=30

SN	Demographic Variables	χ^2 value	df	p value	Level of Significance
1	Age (in years)	6.24	2	0.044	Significant
2	Gestational Age (weeks)	5.18	3	0.159	Not significant
3	Educational Qualification	8.32	3	0.040	Significant
4	Occupation	3.11	2	0.211	Not significant
5	Type of Family	4.27	1	0.039	Significant

Level of significance: $p < 0.05$

The Chi-square test revealed that there was a statistically significant association between the effect of Hoffman's exercise and age ($\chi^2 = 6.24$, $p = 0.044$), educational qualification ($\chi^2 = 8.32$, $p = 0.040$), and type of family ($\chi^2 = 4.27$, $p = 0.039$). However, gestational age ($\chi^2 = 5.18$, $p = 0.159$) and occupation ($\chi^2 = 3.11$, $p = 0.211$) did not show a statistically significant association with the effect of Hoffman's exercise. These findings indicate that demographic variables such as age, educational status, and family type have an influence on the effectiveness of Hoffman's exercise among primigravida mothers.

DISCUSSION

The study was conducted on 30 primigravida mothers using a quasi-experimental one-group pre-test post-test design to evaluate the effectiveness of Hoffman's exercise on nipple protraction and breastfeeding outcomes. The demographic analysis showed that most mothers were young adults, in the later stage of pregnancy, had basic to secondary education, and mainly belonged to nuclear families, which can influence awareness and health practices. Before the intervention, none of the mothers (0%) had normal nipples, and the majority had moderate to severe flat nipples, indicating a high risk for breastfeeding difficulties. After implementing Hoffman's exercise, a noticeable improvement was observed, with 40% of mothers achieving normal nipples and complete elimination of inverted nipples (0%). This clearly shows that the intervention helped in improving nipple protraction. In terms of breastfeeding outcomes, post-interventional LATCH scores revealed that 70% of mothers achieved good breastfeeding status, while fewer mothers remained in moderate and poor categories. This suggests that improved nipple condition positively influenced effective breastfeeding practices. The Chi-square test indicated that factors such as age, educational qualification, and type of family had a significant association with the effectiveness of the intervention, possibly due to better understanding, support, and compliance. However, no significant association was found with gestational age and occupation. Overall, the findings confirm that Hoffman's exercise is an effective, simple, and non-invasive method to improve nipple protraction and enhance breastfeeding outcomes among primigravida mothers.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Hoffman's exercise is an effective intervention for improving nipple protraction and breastfeeding outcomes among primigravida mothers with flat nipples. The findings showed a significant improvement in nipple grading, with an increase in normal nipples (40%) and complete elimination of inverted nipples after the intervention. Additionally, a majority of mothers (70%) achieved good breastfeeding outcomes as per LATCH scores. The statistical analysis further supported the effectiveness of the intervention, showing significant associations with age, educational qualification, and type of family. Overall, the study highlights that early identification and implementation of Hoffman's exercise during the antenatal period can promote successful breastfeeding and improve maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

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